

Two-fluid solar cutoffs

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Magnetoacoustic Cutoff Effect in Numerical Simulations of the Partially-Ionized Solar Atmosphere

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The cutoff effect in the solar atmosphere is a significant determinant of wave propagation and hence pivotal in energy transfer studies, plasma heating, and helioseismology diagnostics. Despite continuous efforts, no good agreement between observed waveperiods and theory or numerical simulations was found. Our objective is to investigate the cutoff effect in the partially-ionised solar atmosphere, factoring in the two-fluid effects. We developed a two-fluid numerical model and used it to simulate a quiet region of the Sun from the top of the convective zone to the low corona above. Our findings show that the ongoing granulation excites a wide range of waves propagating into the upper atmospheric layers, with cutoff waveperiods strongly depending on the height. These numerically obtained two-fluid waveperiods reproduce the recent observations at very good level of compliance. Furthermore, direct comparison with strongly-coupled cases that imitate the single-fluid approximation have shown that the waveperiod propagation pattern is only present in fully two-fluid simulations. We conclude that presence of neutrals and therefore collisional terms change the dynamics of the flow, compared to the single-fluid approximation, especially in the upper photosphere

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1. Introduction

The presence of the cutoff effect in the solar atmosphere and its impact on the propagating waves is one of the fundamental subjects in the field of solar physics. The acoustic cutoff arises naturally in stratified media [1] and its value determines the range of frequencies corresponding to propagating (with frequencies above the cutoff frequency) or evanescent (with frequencies below) waves [2]. Thorough understanding of the cutoff effect is crucial for studies on atmospheric heating, as only the propagating waves contribute to energy flux and can dissipate the carried energy in the upper atmospheric layers [3,4]. Moreover, in the field of helioseismology, the cutoff effect leads to the existence of global p-mode oscillations produced by waves trapped inside the solar interior [5]. Simultaneously, significant efforts are being made with the goal to reveal the connection between cutoff effect and shift of the dominant waveperiod from 5 minutes to 3 minutes in several magnetic structures of the solar atmosphere [6,7], and to explain propagation of the long-period waves in the chromosphere [8–10].

The theoretical formulas for cutoffs were originally derived for acoustic waves in isothermal media. However, the non-isothermal effects turned out to significantly affect the cutoffs variation with height in the solar atmosphere [11–15]. Moreover, as purely acoustic waves are unlikely to exist in the solar atmosphere permeated by magnetic field, other waves were also considered [16–24]. It is important to stress out that despite these numerous and continuous efforts, until now no good agreement between theoretical predictions and observed cutoff frequencies was found.

First observational verification of the variation of acoustic cutoff with height [25] used the HELioseismology Large Regions Interferometric DEvice (HELLRIDE) operating on the Vacuum Tower Telescope (VTT) located on Tenerife to observe waves in the quiet solar atmosphere. Since the magnetic field in quiet regions of the solar atmosphere is weak, the observed waves were predominantly acoustic-gravity waves, whose cutoff frequency and its variations in the solar atmosphere were observationally determined. Nine spectral lines located in the upper photosphere and lower chromosphere were selected and used to perform the measurements. It was showed that none of the analytically derived formula for the cutoff frequency could reproduce their observational results [25].

In another set of observations, the data collected by the Interface Region Imaging Spectrograph (IRIS) was used to establish the existence of acoustic waves and the acoustic cutoff frequency in the quiet solar atmosphere [26]. In these observations, three spectral lines (one in the solar photosphere, one in the chromosphere and one in the transition region) were used and clear variations of the acoustic cutoff in these atmospheric layers were detected. The observations were restricted to quiet solar regions, nevertheless, the effects of magnetic field become important especially for the third spectral line observed in the solar transition region. Again, no currently existing formula for cutoff frequencies could account for these observational results.

The disagreement between the observational and analytical results prompted numerical simulations of cutoff frequencies and their variations in the solar atmosphere [27–32] in which only partial agreements between the data and theory were obtained. Several attempts to specify the crucial factors altering cutoff frequencies were made. In particular, effect of magnetic fields and radiative losses was discussed, with conclusion that they play an important role for determining the evanescent or propagating nature of the waves in quiet-Sun atmospheric regions [31]. Many of these previous studies were done within the framework of magnetohydrodynamics (MHD), which is a good model for a fully ionized plasma. However, the photospheric and chromospheric plasma is partially ionized only, and neutrals play an important role in its dynamics [33] leading to alteration of wave propagation [34–37]. An extremely important implication of the work done with use of two-fluid model on pure acoustic waves [30], and for waves in a quiet region of the solar atmosphere with weak magnetic fields [32], was that the agreement between theory and observations got significantly improved once the effects of partially ionized solar atmosphere were accounted for. Recent work on the global coronal two-fluid model [38] investigated the impact of ion-neutral interactions on the COCONUT

model for space weather prediction [39–41]. In their steady-state studies of the solar corona, the authors found that even when ionization and recombination terms are taken into account, a low concentration of neutrals 10^{-6} persists in the corona on a global scale. These neutrals affect the flow field to a limited but non-negligible extent (up to 5 to 10% locally), with a larger effect in the case of the maximum of the solar activity. The authors hypothesize that stronger magnetic fields of the solar maximum introduce stronger features with higher gradients, velocities, and temperatures, and in such regions both fluids effectively tend to decouple.

In our work we use the recently developed numerical model [32,42] to simulate a quasi-stationary, yet highly dynamic in small scales solar atmosphere, with aim to obtain cutoffs variation with height. The latter take into account interactions between ions and neutrals in partially-ionized plasma and is compared with the recently reported observational data [25,26]. The potential agreement demonstrates the validity of the two-fluid model to describe wave phenomena in quiet regions of the solar atmosphere and may lead to number of implications for plasma heating studies and helioseismology.

This paper is organized as follows. The following section presents the two-fluid model of the solar atmosphere, Section 3 illustrates numerical results, Section 4 discusses comparison with observational findings, and Section 5 provides insight into two-fluid effects and their impact on simulated atmospheric layers. The last Section summarizes our work.

2. Two-fluid model of the solar atmosphere

(a) Two-fluid equations

To simulate a partially-ionized solar atmosphere (which is assumed to consist of hydrogen) in our work we have chosen a two-fluid model. It is widely accepted that such a model is crucially close to the ion-neutral collisions frequencies, thus for sub-second waveperiods. However, as for long waveperiods these two-fluid equations approach two-species MHD equations, we assume their usefulness over simple single-fluid MHD model for much wider range of phenomena. Particularly, in the limit of highly collisional plasma, where ion velocity is close to neutral velocity, $V_i \approx V_n$, while in fact only one momentum equation is required, still two mass conservation equations are needed: one for ions plus electrons and another one for neutrals. This difference change the dynamics of the flow compared to single-fluid MHD approximation and appears to play a role in the wave propagation, plasma heating, Alfvén waves damping etc. [32,43,44]. The two-species MHD model is also widely used in space weather, where the wavelengths and waveperiods are large [45].

We treat ion+electron plasma and neutral gas as dynamic fluids described respectively by MHD and hydrodynamic equations, which are coupled by ion-neutral collisions [46,47]. For the purpose of our studies we modify these equations to include all non-adiabatic and non-ideal terms. The resulting system of evolution equations for neutral gas takes the form:

$$\frac{\partial \varrho_n}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\varrho_n \mathbf{V}_n) = m_n (\Gamma_n^{\text{ion}} + \Gamma_n^{\text{rec}}), \quad (2.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial (\varrho_n \mathbf{V}_n)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\varrho_n \mathbf{V}_n \mathbf{V}_n + p_n \mathbf{I}) = \varrho_n \mathbf{g} + \nabla \cdot \Pi_n + \mathbf{S}_n, \quad (2.2)$$

$$\frac{\partial E_n}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot [(E_n + p_n) \mathbf{V}_n] = (\varrho_n \mathbf{g} + \mathbf{S}_n) \cdot \mathbf{V}_n + Q_n + \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{V}_n \cdot \Pi_n) + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{q}_n - L_n^{\text{r}}, \quad (2.3)$$

and the corresponding equations for plasma supplemented by induction equation takes the form:

$$\frac{\partial \varrho_i}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\varrho_i \mathbf{V}_i) = m_i (\Gamma_i^{\text{ion}} + \Gamma_i^{\text{rec}}), \quad (2.4)$$

$$\frac{\partial (\varrho_i \mathbf{V}_i)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\varrho_i \mathbf{V}_i \mathbf{V}_i + p_{ie} \mathbf{I}) = \varrho_i \mathbf{g} + \frac{1}{\mu} (\nabla \times \mathbf{B}) \times \mathbf{B} + \nabla \cdot \Pi_i + \mathbf{S}_i, \quad (2.5)$$

$$\frac{\partial E_i}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot \left[\left(E_i + p_{ie} + \frac{\mathbf{B}^2}{2\mu} \right) \mathbf{V}_i - \frac{\mathbf{B}}{\mu} (\mathbf{V}_i \cdot \mathbf{B}) \right] + \nabla \cdot \left[\frac{\eta}{\mu} (\nabla \times \mathbf{B}) \times \mathbf{B} \right] =$$

$$(\varrho_i \mathbf{g} + \mathbf{S}_i) \cdot \mathbf{V}_i + Q_i + \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{V}_i \cdot \Pi_i) + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{q}_i - L_r^i + H_r, \quad (2.6)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} = \nabla \times (\mathbf{V}_i \times \mathbf{B}), \quad \nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} = 0. \quad (2.7)$$

The total energy densities of, respectively, neutrals and ions in equations (3) and (6) are described as:

$$E_n = \frac{p_n}{\gamma - 1} + \frac{1}{2} \varrho_n |\mathbf{V}_n|^2, \quad E_i = \frac{p_{ie}}{\gamma - 1} + \frac{1}{2} \varrho_i |\mathbf{V}_i|^2 + \frac{|\mathbf{B}|^2}{2\mu}. \quad (2.8)$$

These two sets of equations are coupled by ion-neutral collisions via friction-like coefficient, α_{in} , linked to ion-neutral collision cross-section, σ_{in} , by the following formula [46,47]

$$\alpha_{in} = \frac{4}{6} \frac{\sigma_{in}}{m_H} \sqrt{\frac{8k_B}{\pi m_H} \left(\frac{T_i}{\mu_i} + \frac{T_n}{\mu_n} \right)} \varrho_i \varrho_n. \quad (2.9)$$

We use here a value of the collision cross-section, σ_{in} , taken from quantum model [48]. Here, symbols ϱ_n (ϱ_i) denote the mass density of the neutrals (ions), \mathbf{V}_n (\mathbf{V}_i) the velocity of the neutrals (ions), p_n (p_{ie}) the neutral (ion+electron) gas pressure, \mathbf{B} the magnetic field, μ the magnetic permeability of the medium, $\gamma = 5/3$ the adiabatic index, T_i (T_n) is the proton (hydrogen atom) temperature, $\mu_{ie} = 1$ and $\mu_n = 1$ are the mean masses of plasma species and neutrals, respectively, m_H is the hydrogen mass, k_B is Boltzmann's constant, $\mathbf{g} = [0, -g, 0]$ the vector of gravitational acceleration with its magnitude $g = 274.78 \text{ m s}^{-2}$, acting along y -axis in Cartesian coordinates. The reaction rates of the electron impact ionization and radiative recombination, $\Gamma_{i,n}^{\text{ion,rec}}$, momentum collisional, $\mathbf{S}_{i,n}$, and energy source, $Q_{i,n}$, terms are described in great details in [42].

Additionally, in our equations Q_i and Q_n denote the heat production/exchange terms resulting from ion-neutral collisions [47], $q_{i,n}$ describe thermal conduction [49] and L_r radiative losses. The latter consists of two separate terms: thick cooling [50] in the low atmospheric layers and thin cooling [51] in the upper atmospheric regions. In order to mimic coronal heating, we supplemented the thin radiative term by the heating term, H_r , which overwhelms the thin radiative cooling term by 99%.

Equations (1)-(9) are supplemented by the ideal gas laws for both neutrals and ions+electrons:

$$p_n = \frac{k_B}{m_H \mu_n} \varrho_n T_n, \quad p_{ie} = 2 \frac{k_B}{m_H \mu_{ie}} \varrho_i T_i. \quad (2.10)$$

(b) Initial state and boundary conditions

The initial ($t = 0$) magnetohydrostatic ($\mathbf{V}_{i,n} = \mathbf{0}$), gravitationally-stratified solar atmosphere is further constructed by deriving equilibrium mass density and gas pressures with the use of hydrostatic equations [52]. This equilibrium is initially overlaid by a range of four magnetic arcades and a vertical magnetic field of its magnitude $B_y = 5 \text{ Gs}$. As the above system is convectively unstable below the photosphere, we perturb it by a small, random signal in V_{iy} which seeds the instability [42].

To solve the set of non-ideal and non-adiabatic equations for two fluids described in details above, we use the JOANNA code [30]. We specified the simulation box along horizontal (x -) and vertical (y -) directions as $(-5.12 < x < 5.12) \text{ Mm} \times (-3.0 < y < 25) \text{ Mm}$. Below the height $y = 17.48 \text{ Mm}$, we set a uniform grid with cell size $20 \text{ km} \times 20 \text{ km}$, while higher up we stretch the grid along y -direction. Such stretched grid absorbs incoming signal and reduces reflections from the upper boundary. At the top and bottom boundaries we fix all plasma quantities to their magnetohydrostatic values, and periodic boundaries are applied in the horizontal direction.

Figure 1. The panels show the temperature (top diagrams) and density (bottom diagrams) profiles for ions (in logarithmic scale). The evolution of the system is shown (from the left to the right) at three different times ($t = 2500$ s, $t = 4500$ s, and $t = 5500$ s). The white lines correspond to the magnetic field lines, and the black arrows denote the velocity field vectors. The arrow's size is normalized according to the maximum magnitude of the velocity field. The vertical black lines (a-d) show the regions used to evaluate the periodograms (see more details in Section 4).

Figure 2. Time-distance plots (related to the y -direction; from the convective zone to the solar corona) for horizontally averaged (between $x = -5.12$ and $x = 5.12$ Mm) ion density (left) and vertical component of ion velocity (right).

3. Numerical results

Within the numerical framework described in the previous section, we investigate now the evolution of a gravitationally stratified and partially ionized solar atmosphere [33,37,46,47]. Figure 1 illustrates how spontaneously generated granulation reshuffles the initial gravitationally stratified magnetohydrostatic equilibrium, which is consistent with typical values for quiet solar regions. A set of convective cells is generated below the photosphere. Hot plasma associated with this granulation drifts towards the chromosphere and forms plasma upflows. At the bottom of the chromosphere the plasma radiates its energy and gets cooled, resulting in the cold plasma downdrafts which settle between granules. Both these upflows and downdrafts with respectively rarefied and dense plasmas are accompanied by two-fluid waves. These waves (namely ion magnetoacoustic-gravity and neutral acoustic-gravity waves) propagate higher up and ultimately penetrate into the solar corona.

Below the photosphere initially vertical magnetic field lines are strongly reshuffled (Fig. 1, top panels, white lines). In between granules few magnetic blobs are formed, some of them later are lifted upwards by hot plasma upflows. At the top of the photosphere, located roughly at $y = 0.5$ Mm, the structure of magnetic carpet is formed, while a few short-living magnetic flux-tubes evolve in time. These flux-tubes act like guidelines for ions and directly affect propagation of magnetoacoustic-gravity waves propagation. The neutral acoustic-gravity waves are affected indirectly only, via ion-neutral collisions and thus their interaction with magnetic field lines depends on how strongly both ion and neutral fluids are coupled. As a result successive of decoupling between plasma and neutral fluid with height, the ion-neutral drift, $V_i - V_n$, increases, and it reaches a magnitude of a few km s^{-1} in the upper chromosphere, transition region and lower corona.

Figure 2 illustrates time-distance plots of the horizontally averaged ion mass density (left) and vertical component of ion velocity (right) generated in the solar atmosphere by ongoing solar granulation. As the outflowing plasma leaves the simulation region, the mass density losses are compensated by plasma inflow, set at the bottom boundary, and radiative losses are compensated mostly by collisional heating in the chromosphere [32]. After the initial transient phase ($t < 2000$ s) our system reaches quasi-stationary state with outflows and downflows being omnipresent in the atmosphere.

4. Simulated and observed periodograms

The obtained numerical results are now directly compared to the observational data collected by HELLRIDE [25] and IRIS [26]. To this aim, we evaluate the periodograms (from a Fourier analysis) for the vertical component of the ion velocity field $V_{iy}(x, y, t)$, assuming several vertical (from -0.5 to 2.5 Mm) and horizontal positions (from -5.12 to 5.12 Mm) from our simulations. Furthermore, we sample the simulated periodograms in time-windows of 1000 s, and apply a short-pass filter (removing periods longer than 300 s) to focus our analysis on the observed wave cutoffs. Note that a detailed comparison of the simulated and observed waveperiods faces several difficulties, mainly because the solar atmosphere is highly dynamical environment and the selected heights above the photopshere are approximated only as they are based on the initial semi-empirical temperature profile. Thus we treat this comparison more in qualitative rather than in quantitative manner.

The top diagrams of each panel of Figure 3 show these periodograms (as a function of height) for 4 horizontal positions (represented by black lines, a-d, in the top diagrams of Figure 1), and at 3 time-windows ($t = 2000 - 3000$ s, $t = 4000 - 5000$ s, and $t = 5000 - 6000$ s)¹. Once obtained the spectra, we evaluated the weighted by normalized amplitudes higher than 0.7 average values of the periods. (blue circles in the bottom diagrams of each panel of Figure 3) and the respective standard deviations (blue-shaded regions). Although the sample of the observational data may be small (represented by diamond and dot symbols), we selected the best-fit periodograms from

¹The diagrams of Figure 1 correspond to the middle time of each time-window used in the Fourier spectrum.

Figure 3. Periodograms for the vertical component of ion velocity field ($V_{iy}(x, y, t)$). The letters on the top-left of each panel (a-d) indicate the regions, in Figure 1, where the periodograms were taken. The top diagrams of each panel represent the Fourier spectrum, and the bottom ones (with blue circles) correspond to the period's weighted average values with normalized amplitude higher than 0.7 (the blue-shaded regions indicate the standard deviations). The diamonds and dots show the observational data obtained by [25] and [26] (with error bars), respectively.

a χ^2 -test with a p-level of significance higher than 0.01 (using the weighted average values from our simulations). We clearly see the change of main waveperiod of the outflows associated with V_{iy} . The waves with periods between 200 s and 300 s, are evanescent in the photosphere, and thus the wave package propagating into the chromosphere and corona consists of waveperiods between 100 and 200 s. Most long waveperiods, close to 5-minutes, are generated by strongly turbulent plasma below the photosphere.

At the top of the photosphere, where two-fluid waves are subject of reflection and cutoff frequencies, the main waveperiod quickly decreases. At the bottom of the chromosphere the dominant waveperiods are 180 s and 150 s. Waves with these waveperiods propagate up to the transition region and into the corona. Despite the fact that at the transition region few accompanying waveperiods are secondarily generated (e.g. 120 s) the former remain dominant. We infer that the waveperiod follows the observational data, and conclude that the description of the solar atmospheric plasma in the framework of two-fluid equations for ions and neutrals demonstrates a good agreement between numerically detected periods of the waves, which are generated by the solar granulation and the observational data.

Note that there is also a lot of waveperiods outside the observational ranges at different heights in Fig. 3. Especially the layers of upper chromosphere and lower corona are filled with wide range of waveperiods. With lack of the detailed observations of the cutoffs in these regions we imply

Figure 4. Time-distance plots (from the photosphere to the lower corona) of the ion-neutral drift, $|V_i - V_n|$. From top-left to bottom-right: the original case, the case of α_{in} multiplied by factor of 10, 10^2 and 10^3 .

that these should be proposed as targets for future observations. However, the main waveperiod shows an unprecedented agreement with the trend framed by the observational data presented here. First such a comparison [25], directly compared the observational data with analytical predictions made by using different formulas for the cutoffs [11–14,19], and concluded that major improvements are needed in theories of cutoffs in order to account for the observed variations of the observed cutoffs in the solar atmosphere. In the followed up works the performed numerical simulations have achieved partial agreements with the observational data [27–32,42]. The results presented in this paper are in much better agreement with the data than in any previous work. Thus, our main conclusion is that the effects of partially ionized solar atmosphere, radiation, thermal conduction, and weak magnetic fields must all be accounted for in order to reproduce theoretically the observed variations of the cutoffs in the solar atmosphere.

5. Two-fluid effects

We now investigate the ion-neutral effects in the quasi-stationary solar atmosphere perturbed by the ongoing granulation. Our goal is to determine if granulation-generated ion and neutral waves decouple while propagating into the solar atmosphere, and if yes - what is the magnitude of the ion-neutral drift and which atmospheric layers are affected the most. This in turn will help us to determine the impact of two-fluid effects on waveperiod pattern in the simulations we performed.

We compare here the original two-fluid case with three separate test-cases corresponding to artificially increased coupling between ion and neutral fluids, with the frictional coefficient, α_{in} , multiplied by factor of 10, 10^2 , and 10^3 . The increased coupling between both fluids result in reduction of any possible two-fluid effects (wave damping, frictional heating), in extreme case leading to plasma behaviour close to single-fluid MHD.

Figure 5. Time-distance plots (from the photosphere to the lower corona) of the ion temperature, T_i . From top-left to bottom-right: the original case, the case of α_{in} multiplied by factor of 10, 10^2 and 10^3 .

Figure 6. The averaged over time ion temperature profile, $\langle T_i \rangle$, (solid line) vs initial temperature profile (dotted line), the original case (left) and the case with α_{in} multiplied by factor of 10^3 (right).

Figure 4 shows time-distance plots of the ion-neutral drift, $|V_i - V_n|$, in four discussed cases (from top-left to bottom-right). The ion-neutral drift is first and most important indicator of two-fluid effects. In the original case both fluids start to decouple in the temperature minimum layer ($y = 0.5$ Mm above the photosphere). The ion-neutral drift increases with height, however its value remains in general below 0.1 km s^{-1} . Higher up, close to the transition region it exceeds 1 km s^{-1} and ion-neutral waves enter the low corona essentially decoupled. It is noteworthy that ion-neutral drift is persistent in discussed atmospheric layers and is not an episodic event.

Figure 7. Periodograms for the vertical component of ion velocity field, $V_{iy}(x, y, t)$. From top-left to bottom-right: the original case, the case of α_{in} multiplied by factor of 10, 10^2 , and 10^3 .

Figure 4 (top-right) illustrates the case of α_{in} increased 10 times. Significant reduction of ion-neutral velocity drift is clearly visible, which, while still present in the chromosphere is now of the order of 1 m s^{-1} , and only episodically exceeds 10^2 m s^{-1} in the lower corona. In the case of α_{in} multiplied by factor of 10^2 (Fig. 4, bottom-left) chromospheric plasma and neutral gas remain for most of the time fully coupled, with ion-neutral drift of the order of 1 cm s^{-1} . Further increase of α_{in} couples both fluids even stronger. Only small eruptions and jets lead sporadically to larger gradients and slight (order of 1 m s^{-1}) decoupling in the lower corona (of the order of 1 m s^{-1}).

Figure 5 illustrates the four corresponding time-distance plots of the ion temperature, T_i , for α_{in} varying from original to its value multiplied by factor of 10^3 (from top-left to bottom-right). While the simulated solar atmosphere is still highly dynamic in all the discussed cases, the delicate balance between collisional heating and radiative cooling is disturbed for the fully-coupled case, which results in the decrease of average temperature, significant oscillations of the transition region and larger number of eruptions from the chromosphere into the corona. However, the most important conclusion here is that the changes in temperature profile, while clearly visible, are by average relatively small, especially in the upper photosphere and the chromosphere and thus cannot affect general properties of propagating waves. The corresponding averaged over time ion temperature profile, $\langle T_i \rangle$, is shown in Fig. 6. The major difference between the original case (left) and the case with α_{in} multiplied by factor of 10^3 (right) takes place at the transition region and in the lower corona. In the latter case $\langle T_i \rangle$ tends to decrease due to the lack of collisional heating.

The Fourier spectra of waveperiods propagating through the solar atmosphere in the discussed cases are illustrated in Fig. 7. In the original case we see the decrease of the waveperiods that occurs in the lower and middle chromosphere. Comparing with Fig. 4 we indicate that this decrease occurs in atmospheric layers where both fluids start to decouple. The originally generated longer waveperiods are reduced there to values below 200 s. Higher up, longer waveperiods become dominant again and propagate through the transition region into the lower corona. Conversely, in the artificially coupled cases the originally excited waveperiods tend to freely propagate through the lower and middle chromosphere. The two most prominent marks of the observational results (Fig. 3) are: (a) decrease of waveperiods below $P = 200$ s near the temperature minimum, and (b) increase of waveperiods in the upper chromosphere. Both these features are present in the original two-fluid case only. While the first is still distinguishable in the case of α_{in} multiplied by factor of 10 (Fig. 7, top-right), the full-coupled case reveals complete lack of the discussed features (Fig. 7, bottom-right), with the waveperiod of $P = 230$ s being dominant over entire chromosphere.

6. Conclusion

We reported for the first time numerically obtained cutoff waveperiods that remain in good agreement with the observational data [25,26]. With use of the JOANNA code we performed numerical simulations of two-fluid realistic, spontaneously evolving solar granulation and waves excited in a partially ionized solar atmosphere, with a weak magnetic field and the effects of radiation and thermal conduction included. We found that in the sub-photospheric regions of highly turbulent and strongly coupled plasma the main period of excited waves is close to 300 s. This period quickly falls off to value below 200 s in the upper photosphere. While in the low chromosphere, where both fluids decouple, the main waveperiod decreases further to 180 s and 150 s. In the upper chromospheric layers longer waveperiods become dominant again and propagate through the transition region into the lower corona. We showed that this pattern is present in two-fluids simulations only and disappears when stronger coupling between both ion and neutral fluids is invoked. Our results improve to great extent the cutoff frequencies computed/obtained before [52,53].

The presented results have important implications for a number of branches in the solar physics. As HD and MHD models ultimately failed to predict the observations, the two-fluid model appears to be more appropriate for studies of waves and wave-driven processes in the partially-ionized solar atmosphere. This should be expected as plasma in the chromosphere is dominated by neutrals and therefore their role should not be omitted. First, studies that aim to answer the ongoing question of plasma heating and energy balance in the solar atmosphere should take two-fluid effects into account. Not only two-fluid cutoff effect determines which waves actually propagate into the higher layers of the solar atmosphere, as it was shown in our studies, but ion-neutral collisions lead to wave energy dissipation in frictional heating and contribute to the overall chromospheric heating [42,54]. The two-fluid approach seems also to be important for helioseismology, with two-fluid cutoffs effect potentially affecting the shift of the dominant waveperiod from 5 minutes to 3 minutes in several magnetic structures of the solar atmosphere, as well as propagation of the long-period waves in the chromosphere. This will require further studies in the future. It is also worth mentioning here, that although we aim to recreate the observational data here, our results may conversely be used for observational purposes. The two-fluid cutoffs may be important for observations as well, determining the observational targets for future generation of the ground- and space-borne missions.

We conclude that the two-fluid effects are a long overlooked factor significantly altering cutoffs and as a result all wave processes in the solar atmosphere.

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